

ES30029: Final Year Research Project

Analysing the Impact of ESG Factors on Stock Market Performance in Crisis and Non-Crisis Periods: Evidence from U.S. Equities During the COVID-19 Pandemic

Tim Bird

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Abstract

This dissertation investigates the impact of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) factors on stock market performance across crisis and non-crisis periods in the United States, with a specific focus on the COVID-19 pandemic. By employing a fixed effects Panel Least Squares regression and focusing on monthly abnormal returns (MAR) as the dependent variable, this study analyses ESG's role in shaping stock performance under different market conditions. The research finds no significant relationship between ESG factors and abnormal returns in the pre-crisis period, aligning with existing literature. However, a significant negative relationship is observed during the crisis period, especially among firms with higher ESG scores. The governance dimension of ESG predominantly influences this negative relationship. This dissertation discusses these findings in the context of potential shifts in investor behaviour during crises, suggesting that ESG may not act as an "equity vaccine" in times of market uncertainty, contrary to some industry claims.

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1.0 Introduction

In recent years, sustainable investment strategies have gained considerable momentum, with ESG factors serving as the key metric for assessing a firm's sustainability. This surge is propelled by global initiatives like the Paris Agreement and Sustainable Development Goals, highlighting the urgent need to address climate change and social challenges. Against this backdrop, investigating the relationship between sustainable investments and stock returns becomes paramount. Understanding this relationship not only shapes investment decisions but influences the alignment of portfolios with global sustainability objectives. Moreover, examining ESG resilience during crises, such as the COVID-19 pandemic, offers insights into the viability of ESG as an “equity vaccine” (Willis, 2020). While numerous studies have explored this relationship across various regions, no definitive conclusion has emerged regarding the impact of ESG integration on stock market performance.

This dissertation contributes to the literature in several ways. Firstly, this study ventures beyond the conventional scope by extending the crisis period beyond the initial market crash in the first quarter of 2020. By doing so, it seeks to delve deeper into the relationship between sustainable investing and stock market performance, encompassing the period until investor sentiment stabilised and markets regained stability. Extending the crisis period allows us to examine the relationship throughout the entirety of the COVID-19 crisis, providing a comprehensive and robust analysis on sustainable investing and stock market performance during the pandemic. Secondly, as far as I am aware, no COVID-19 study in the US has tested for disaggregated ESG scores. This study looks to assess whether any specific dimension of ESG drives stock returns. Lastly, as a robustness check, I conduct a quartile regression to bolster the reliability of the findings. This analysis offers further insights, suggesting that the relationship between ESG and stock market performance could be primarily influenced by firms in the upper two quartiles of ESG scores. Together, these contributions enrich the limited and divided literature on the topic, enhancing our understanding of the relationship between sustainable investing and stock returns and offering valuable insights for investors, policymakers, and researchers alike.

An extensive literature review reveals that Demers et al. (2021) and Lins et al. (2017) present the most robust research on ESG during crises. Hence, I utilise these studies to shape the methodological approach adopted in this dissertation. The Refinitiv ESG score is chosen as a proxy for ESG due to its comprehensive coverage compared to other available scores. The pre-crisis period is defined as spanning from January 2017 to February 2020, with the crisis period lasting from March 2020 to December 2021.

My model is a fixed effects Panel Least Squares regression, using monthly abnormal returns (MAR) for the pre-crisis and crisis periods as the dependent variable and ESG scores as the primary variable of interest. I find no significant relationship between ESG and abnormal returns during the pre-crisis period, consistent with much of the key literature. However, in the crisis period, I find that ESG scores have a significant negative impact on stock performance. Additionally, my results reveal that among the ESG factors, the governance dimension predominantly influenced the negative relationship with stock market performance. Furthermore, I demonstrate that this negative impact was particularly pronounced for firms scoring in the upper two quartiles of ESG ratings.

The structure of this dissertation is as follows: Section 2 details the background on the rise of ESG investing and gives an overview of the COVID-19 pandemic. Section 3 presents thorough literature review, where I critically appraise crisis and non-crisis studies before determining the most robust literature for which I build this study on. Section 4 details my methodology and section 5 presents my data and in depth analysis of my findings. Section 6 concludes the study and identifies policy recommendations, scope for future studies as well as discussing the limitations of this dissertation.

2.0 Background

2.1 ESG Investing

ESG investing originated back in the 1960s as socially responsible investing. During this time, investors began to exclude stocks or entire industries from their portfolios based on particular business activities, such as tobacco production or involvement in the South African apartheid regime (MSCI, 2023). The expansion of ESG investments gained momentum in 2013-2014, coinciding with the publication of initial studies demonstrating a positive correlation between corporate sustainability and financial performance (Kell, 2018). In recent years, ESG investments have witnessed unprecedented growth. Global ESG assets are projected to surpass \$50 trillion by 2025, equal to one third of the projected assets under management globally (Bloomberg, 2022). This trend continues the growth of ESG assets, after they surpassed \$35 trillion in 2020, highlighting a significant shift in investor priorities towards ESG. The momentum behind sustainable investing is driven by bottom-up demand, with investors at all levels increasingly allocating their capital towards sustainable strategies. From individual savers to institutional investors, there is a growing trend of using investment portfolios to contribute towards building a more sustainable world (J.P. Morgan Asset Management, 2022). According to deal data provider PitchBook, 61% of North American investors applied ESG criteria to at least part of their portfolio in 2022, up from 58% in 2021 (Arjaliès, 2023). A recent report by Morgan Stanley (2023), stated that investors have attributed their increasing interest in sustainable investing to various factors, with a significant portion citing recent advancements in climate science (53%) and the favourable financial performance of sustainable investments (52%). Furthermore, they state that most investors express the belief that companies ought to address environmental and social concerns in their operations. In line with investor expectations, McKinsey's latest Global Survey states that 93% of respondents say at least one ESG dimension is on their organisation's agenda. Furthermore, they report that the majority (57%) of professional investors and executives surveyed believe ESG programs create shareholder value (McKinsey & Company, 2020). As investors increasingly prioritise sustainability alongside financial returns, there is a heightened

importance to explore the relationship between ESG factors and stock market returns, particularly in the context of significant market crises like the COVID-19 pandemic.

While ESG investing has gained significant momentum, concerns are emerging about its potential slowdown. According to the latest assessment by the Global Sustainable Investment Alliance (GSIA), in the US, investor holdings in sustainable assets fell to \$8.4 trillion in 2022, from \$17 trillion two years prior. Additionally, the interest in sustainable investing soared during the pandemic, as lockdowns caused energy prices to fall and rewarded portfolios that divested from fossil fuels. However, as restrictions eased and economic activity returned, energy prices rose, making ESG strategies less profitable (Marsh, 2023).

2.2 COVID-19 Pandemic

On January 30, 2020, the World Health Organization (WHO, 2020) declared the COVID-19 outbreak a global public health emergency, prompted by over 7,000 reported cases worldwide. Subsequently, the spread of COVID-19 accelerated, and by March 11, 2020, the WHO (2020) officially classified it as a global pandemic. This declaration caused widespread societal lockdowns across many regions, with approximately half of the world's population under lockdown by April 2020 (Sandford, 2020). Moreover, it brought about an unprecedented steep and rapid decline in the global capital markets. Baker et al. (2020) state that no infectious disease, including the Spanish Flu, has ever had the same impact on the global markets as the COVID-19 pandemic did.

2.3 The Stock Market Crash

The International Monetary Fund declared the pandemic as the most severe economic crisis since the Great Depression (Gopinath, 2020). According to Li (2020), the S&P 500 experienced a rapid decline of 30% from its peak on February 19, in just 22 trading days. This remarkable speed marked the fastest drop of this magnitude in history. The steep decline of the S&P 500 prompted level-1 trading curbs, leading major US stock markets to suspend trading for 15 minutes on March 9, 2020, March 12, 2020, March 16, 2020, and March 18, 2020, respectively. Given that over the past 33 years such

trading curbs had only been triggered once before, on October 27, 1997, the four instances of triggering within a span of 10 days were unprecedented and generated substantial uncertainty among investors (Shu et al., 2021). Li et al. (2022) observed that COVID-19 fears significantly heightened market volatility and reduced stock returns. Albulescu (2021) and Yousfi et al. (2021) confirmed these findings in the US markets and demonstrated a long-term correlation between the US stock market, the CBOE Volatility Index (VIX), and global daily COVID-19 cases and deaths during the pandemic's first wave. This correlation persisted into the second wave, even after easing quarantine restrictions.

2.4 The Recovery

However, following this sharp decline, the US markets embarked on an extraordinary bull run throughout the remainder of the year, with numerous indexes and stocks reaching record highs. With US unemployment figures rising, the economy shut down, and no vaccine in sight, this seemed impossible. However, the Fed stepped in by cutting interest rates to near zero and introducing a \$2.3 trillion fiscal rescue package, providing a lifeline to the market, businesses, and households (Frazier, 2021). By August 2020, the S&P500 reached a new all-time high, becoming the “fastest recovery ever” (Jasinski, 2020). This rapid recovery prompted early studies examining the crisis, (Demers et al., 2021; Albuquerque et al., 2020; Ding et al., 2020), to classify this bull run as the “rebound period”.

2.5 The Second and Third Wave

Following the initial onset of the pandemic and the first wave of cases, subsequent waves emerged, notably the second wave during the winter months of 2020-2021. This surge prompted widespread vaccination efforts, with FDA-authorized vaccines becoming available by December 2020, leading to a decline in infection rates through the spring of 2021 (Maragakis, 2021). However, the emergence of the highly transmissible delta variant fuelled a third wave, commencing in July 2021. By the end of 2021, infection rates had once again decreased, accompanied by a relaxation of restrictions across the US. These developments underscore the need to extend the crisis

period beyond the initial market crash, to encompass the broader impact of the pandemic on market dynamics and investor behaviour. I elaborate on this further in the methodology when defining the crisis period.

2.6 Downside Risk Mitigation

In the aftermath of the crash, there were several claims that strong ESG performance acted as a downside risk mitigator. In April 2020, Morningstar had already labelled ESG as an “equity vaccine”, stating that ESG investments had demonstrated greater resilience to the crash compared to other investments (Willis, 2020). This is supported by the findings of Dai (2022), who conclude ESG investing emerges as a safe haven during crises. According to the Morgan Stanley Institute for Sustainable Investing (2021), US sustainable equity funds outperformed traditional funds by a median total return of 4.3%. Additionally, the median downside deviation of US sustainable equity funds was 3.1% less than that of traditional funds. Polman (2020) suggests that businesses committed to all their stakeholders rather than just shareholders, and pursue a purpose beyond profit, may be inherently more resilient amidst ongoing health crises and economic challenges. This supports the notion that ESG activities mitigate downside risk during economic downturns by fostering investors' confidence and trust in the company (Lins et al., 2017). I discuss this in further detail in the literature review.

3.0 Literature Review

3.1 ESG and Stock Market Performance

Existing literature on this topic, generally finds a positive or insignificant relationship between ESG activities and stock market performance. Meta-analyses by Orlitzky et al. (2003) and Busch and Friede (2018) demonstrate a highly significant, positive, robust, and bilateral relationship between ESG activities and corporate financial performance (CFP). Friede et al. (2015) analysed approximately 2,200 studies on ESG and financial performance, revealing that the majority of studies demonstrate a positive or insignificant connection, with significant geographical variations. Some studies observe a notably stronger ESG-CFP relationship US assets in comparison to non-US assets (Allouche and Laroche 2005; Dixon-Fowler et al. 2013). In North America, the focus of this dissertation, 42.7% of studies revealed a positive correlation, with 51.3% yielding non-significant correlations, compared with Europe's 26.1% and 65.9% respectively. Additionally, Friede et al. (2015) examine whether any of the three ESG components have a predominant impact on CFP, revealing that some meta-analyses find significant positive relations for corporate environmental performance and CFP (Albertini 2013; Dixon-Fowler et al. 2013; Endrikat, Guenther, and Hoppe 2014). There also are several studies that support a positive correlation between corporate governance performance and CFP (Dalton et al. 1999; Gillan and Starks 2007; Love 2011). Albuquerque et al. (2020) highlight the difficulty in identifying the direction of causality – do ESG activities create value for shareholders, or can highly performing firms afford to invest in ESG activities?

While many studies support the notion that firms derive value from ESG investments, other literature finds its impact on stock performance insignificant or irrelevant. In a meta-analysis, Revelli and Viviani (2014) reviewed 85 studies and 190 experiments spanning 20 years. They find that, globally, no definitive conclusion can be drawn regarding whether socially responsible investing (SRI) is positively or negatively correlated with stock market performance. Supporting this conclusion, recent global data examined by Sargis and Wang (2020) found no significant link between ESG and returns. Demers et al., (2021) discuss the relationship from an agency theory

perspective, a notion typically attributed to Friedman (1970). This more sceptical outlook suggests that executives might opt to enhance their company's ESG scores aiming to bolster their personal reputations at the expense of shareholders. This reputation-building, contributing to reduced turnover risk, is viewed as part of the executive's entrenchment strategy to reduce the likelihood of replacement, resulting in negative effects on financial performance (Surroca & Tribó, 2008). If such ESG investments lead to managerial entrenchment or are perceived as wasteful self-serving expenditures funded from corporate funds, they could ultimately diminish shareholder value. Supporting this notion, Lys et al. (2015) demonstrate that although CSR investments signal anticipation of stronger future performance, they do not inherently create value for the business. Hence, ESG expenditures may yield insufficient returns, reducing shareholder value, and increasing vulnerability during a crisis.

Overall, the literature is divided as to whether ESG investments have yielded discernible positive abnormal returns in recent years. Giese et al. (2019) highlight variations in study findings, attributing them to methodological differences and disparities in databases. The authors also critique past research for its failure to identify economic mechanisms explaining the link between ESG and corporate financial performance.

3.2 ESG and Resilience

The existing literature within SRI reveals that investors with sustainable preferences exhibit lower sensitivity to the performance of SRI funds compared to conventional funds (Bollen, 2007; Renneboog et al., 2011). In the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, where investors' risk attitudes may be altered, the SRI literature generally suggests that ESG investors display greater resilience than their counterparts. Hoepner et al. (2016) contribute evidence supporting the idea that engagement in ESG issues benefits shareholders by mitigating firms' downside risk, with the environmental element of ESG being the most impactful. Sassen et al. (2016) show that higher CSR reduces both total and idiosyncratic risk for European firms. Modelling CSR as an investment in increased product differentiation, Albuquerque et al. (2018) argue that CSR leads to decreased systematic risk, enhanced profits, and has the most significant impact on firms characterised by high product differentiation.

3.3 ESG and 2008-2009 Global Financial Crisis

Empirical studies on the impact of ESG in crises is somewhat limited. The most extensive research into this topic was a study by Lins et al. (2017), which examined the impact on US stocks during the financial crisis. The authors argue that companies with a high social capital score, measured by CSR intensity, yield higher returns compared to those with lower social capital scores. Furthermore, they argue that ESG activities help to mitigate downside risk during economic downturns by allowing companies to enhance their social reputation, thereby fostering investors' confidence and trust in the company. Lins et al. (2017) described this as a type of “insurance policy”, implying that when the overall degree of trust in firms and markets experiences a negative shock, the trust that a company and its investors have developed through social capital investments pays dividends through mitigating downside risk (Godfrey et al., 2008). Although there was no significant difference in stock return performance during the post-crisis recovery, the sustained absence of a reversal emphasises the enduring importance of trust. Their study also concluded that high-CSR firms exhibited increased profitability, margins, sales growth, and employee productivity during crises, indicating that greater social capital translates to higher returns at the microeconomic level. Furthermore, in crises, external shareholders may express concerns that traditional financial data may lack credibility, resulting in a shift towards nonfinancial indicators such as ESG ratings. These indicators, reflecting a firm's values and integrity, may be considered more reliable, leading to a valuation premium on firms perceived as more trustworthy (Lins et al., 2017). A study conducted by Cornett et al. (2016), presents evidence indicating that banks benefit from engaging in socially responsible practices, as demonstrated by a positive relationship between Return on Equity (ROE) and Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) scores. The authors propose that increased involvement in CSR activities following the global financial crisis is likely to result in a decreased likelihood of future market crashes.

Another study by Bouslah et al. (2018) indicates a significant difference in the relationship between risk and social performance during crisis and pre-crisis periods. The authors reveal that CSR contributes to a reduction in volatility during financial crises. Additionally, this risk reduction is primarily attributed to the strength's component rather than the concerns component of social performance. Hence, they

conclude that CSR acts as a risk-mitigating measure during market turmoil. Nofsinger and Varma (2014) find SRI funds outperform conventional funds during crises and underperform during non-crisis periods based on their analysis of US funds from 2000 to 2011. In contrast, Leite and Cortez (2015) conducted a study on French SRI funds investing in Europe from 2001-2012. They find no positive effect of ESG during the financial crisis, with French SRI funds underperforming in non-crisis periods, and not providing any downside protection during the crisis, instead matching similar conventional funds.

Albuquerque et al. (2020) emphasise the differences between the COVID-19 crisis and the global financial crisis of 2008-2009, highlighting the unpredictability and shorter duration of the former. They argue that, unlike the financial crisis, the COVID-19 crisis is an exogenous health shock, making it more suitable for observing the impact of ESG on stock market performance. Dai et al. (2020) demonstrate that companies tend to increase their ESG score during economic uncertainty. Despite the vastly different causes of the two crises, both led to significant stock price movements. Takahashi and Yamada (2020) note similarities between the two crises, including financial institution fire sales, trade shrinkage, and high debt in the social sector, suggesting that research from the financial crisis may offer insights applicable to the COVID-19 crisis.

3.4 ESG and the COVID-19 Stock Market Crash

Several studies have investigated the relationship between ESG activities and stock market performance during the COVID-19 pandemic. Albuquerque et al. (2020), produced an analysis of the COVID-19 stock market crash based on ESG data from a sample of more than 2,000 US equities. Their approach consisted of a cross-sectional model, regressing abnormal returns from Q1 2020 on ESG scores and several firm controls. The authors concluded that stocks with higher ES ratings generated significantly higher returns and reduced volatility in returns during Q1 of 2020.

Ding et al. (2020) explored the relationship between corporate characteristics and stock returns in response to the COVID-19 market crash, analysing data from over 6000 stocks across 56 economies. A significant discovery from their research is that share

price declines induced by the pandemic were inversely related to the companies' ESG scores, suggesting that firms engaging in more CSR activities experienced a less severe decline in stock returns. The authors posit that this aligns with the perspective that CSR initiatives enhance the relationship between the company and its stakeholders. By fostering loyalty and stronger relationships with key stakeholders, CSR empowers the firm to collaborate more effectively with these stakeholders in navigating the challenges posed by the pandemic, enabling stronger financial performance.

Demers et al. (2021) provide evidence indicating that abnormal returns are not significantly impacted by ESG in the US during the COVID-19 crisis. The authors employ a panel data model regressing Buy-and-hold abnormal returns (BHAR) on Refinitiv ESG scores, Fama-French factors as well as several firm specific controls. Their study reveals ESG is not significant in the first quarter of 2020, characterised as the crisis period, and find a negative association with returns in the second quarter of 2020, identified as the market recovery period. In contrast to similar research conducted by Albuquerque et al. (2020) and Ding et al. (2020), Demers et al. (2021) apply additional control variables known to be theoretically or empirically correlated with returns and ESG. They emphasise the importance of financial flexibility for a firm's performance during the crisis and highlight the significance of investments in internally generated intangible assets in explaining abnormal returns for both periods. Additionally, the authors challenge the validity of the studies by Albuquerque et al. (2020) and Ding et al. (2020), identifying omitted variables bias in both studies. They argue that the analyses lack controls for traditional market-based risk measures and various other variables that are closely linked to returns and firms' ESG scores. Demers et al. (2021) suggest that, in the US market, there is more discussion than action regarding ESG, differing from Europe where ESG is taken more seriously. Notably, their study focuses solely on US stocks, contrasting with Ding et al. (2020), who analyse a global sample primarily comprising non-US stocks. Demers et al. (2021) argue that Ding et al. (2020)'s findings may not directly apply to US stocks, emphasising the generalisability of their own study to a US-only context. Drange & Olav (2021) expand upon the research by Demers et al. (2021), focusing on the Nordic region. Their results match the findings of Demers et al. (2021) despite geographical differences. This underscores the literature's emphasis on further studies to determine potential geographical variations in the impact of ESG.

An examination of the Japanese stock market during COVID-19 by Liu et al. (2023) revealed several insights. After controlling for several corporate factors and COVID-19 exposure, their analysis of over 300 listed firms indicated that ESG performance had a substantial impact on stock returns during the pandemic. Furthermore, the authors concluded that enhanced ESG performance not only contributed to heightened stock market liquidity but also dampened volatility throughout the observed period. Dai (2022) examine ESG as an “equity vaccine” during crises, focusing on the Wuhan and Shanghai lockdowns in China. Their research reveals that ESG equity indices exhibit reduced risk compared to conventional benchmark indices, demonstrating resilience throughout the periods of both lockdowns. Hence, they conclude ESG investing emerges as a safe haven during crises, particularly in the context of China.

On the other hand, Takahashi and Yamada (2020) conduct a similar study, examining the Japanese stock market during COVID-19. However, they find no evidence that ESG is associated with abnormal returns during the pandemic. They highlight that ESG may have a different meaning in Asia compared with Europe and the US, where the ESG-concept originated from. The authors acknowledge that the sample size used in their ESG-analysis is a small fraction of the total sample and therefore there may be some biases. Nonetheless, the study underscores the impact of ESG and supports the notion of geographical variations in its influence.

3.5 Tying the Literature to this Dissertation

The literature reviewed in this section does not provide a global consensus on the impact of ESG on stock market returns during crises, with a high degree of variation among regions. In non-crisis periods, the literature tends to reach a consistent conclusion where ESG has no significant effect on abnormal returns. However, concerning ESG's role during crises, the literature is more limited and exhibits differing perspectives. Notably, Lins et al. (2017) and Demers et al. (2021) stand out as conducting the most robust research on ESG during crises. As such this dissertation will build upon their work, looking to test the impact of ESG on the US stock market both during and prior to the COVID-19 pandemic.

4.0 Methodology

4.1 The Pre-Crisis Period

The start of my pre-crisis period is defined by the earliest date for which ESG scores are available for the firms in my sample, which is January 2017. Subsequently, the pre-crisis period extends until the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic lockdown in the USA, marked by a significant decline in the CBOE Volatility Index (VIX). According to Jacobsen and Jacobsen (2020), the first COVID-19 restrictions in the US were implemented on March 12, 2020, corresponding roughly to the sharp decrease in the VIX in March. Therefore, we designate the end of February 2020 as the conclusion of our pre-crisis period and the beginning of March 2020 as the commencement of the crisis period.

4.2 The Crisis Period

There is substantial variation in the literature as to what date constitutes the end crisis period. Demers et al. (2021), Takahashi and Yamada (2020), and Albuquerque et al, (2020), among others, define the crisis period as Q1 of 2020. However, these papers were published amid the pandemic and therefore did not have the benefit of conducting their studies after the COVID crisis had ended. I define the end of crisis period as the point at which stability and investor sentiment in the US stock market returned to pre-pandemic levels.

Figure 1 shows that by the end of 2021, the VIX, an indicator of investor sentiment and market volatility, had returned to pre-pandemic levels. This suggests that investor confidence was on the rise, as evidenced by reduced fear and uncertainty. It also indicates that economic conditions were stabilising, as lower volatility typically corresponds to a more stable market environment. Overall, the normalisation of the VIX to pre-pandemic levels signifies a restoration of market confidence and a potential return to business as usual in the financial markets. Based on this, I deem it appropriate to extend the crisis period to the end of 2021 in this study.

Figure 1: CBOE Volatility Index (VIX)

Source: *Yahoo Finance: Available at*

<https://uk.finance.yahoo.com/quote/%5EVIX?.tsrc=fin-srch>

4.3 Factor Models

The Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM)

The CAPM describes a linear relationship between systematic risk and expected return for an asset. It was formed on the principle that investors require compensation for both the time value of money and the asset's susceptibility to market movements. This model originated from Markowitz's (1952) and was subsequently introduced separately by Sharpe (1964), Lintner (1965), and Mossin (1966). The CAPM is given in equation 1.

$$E(r_{i,t}) = r_f + \beta_1(E(r_m) - r_f) \quad (1)$$

where:

$E(r_{i,t})$ = Expected return of the stock

r_f = risk-free rate

β_1 = The beta of the stock. The slope coefficient, measuring the sensitivity of the asset to the market.

$(E(r_m) - r_f)$ = The market risk premium, depicted as Market_RF.

Fama-French Three-Factor Model

Fama and French (1993) enhanced the CAPM by introducing two additional factors, as shown in equation 2. These factors historically explain more of the variance than the error term in the CAPM would have captured. This model represented a significant advancement from the CAPM, capturing approximately 90% of the variance in a diversified portfolio, compared to the CAPM's 70%.

$$E(r_{i,t}) = r_f + \beta_1(E(r_m) - r_f) + \beta_2(HML_t) + \beta_3(SMB_t) \quad (2)$$

Carhart four-factor Model

Carhart (1997) observed a correlation between current and past returns. This prompted them to expand the Fama-French three factor model to include a momentum factor to explain more of the return variance. The model is depicted in equation 3.

$$E(r_{i,t}) = r_f + \beta_1(E(r_m) - r_f) + \beta_2(HML_t) + \beta_3(SMB_t) + \beta_4(Momentum_t) \quad (3)$$

4.4 ESG Variable

Given my dataset's longer time span, I assessed the stationarity of the ESG variable, differing from the methodology of the existing literature, often constrained by shorter timeframes. Initially, unit-root tests on the raw ESG scores revealed non-stationarity, prompting a logarithmic transformation of the ESG variable and its individual pillars. Despite this, subsequent unit-root tests persisted in indicating the presence of a unit-root. Consequently, I applied first-order differencing to the logged ESG variable, successfully rendering it stationary. The same method was done for each of the pillars of ESG for the disaggregated model.

Additionally, I performed a Modified Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) test to ascertain the appropriate lag length for the independent variables in my model. By applying this test, I aimed to identify the lag length that minimises information loss and avoids overfitting. This approach ensures robustness and enhances the reliability of the

empirical analysis by determining the most suitable specification for the independent variables within the panel data framework.

4.5 Abnormal Returns

To investigate the impact of ESG on stock returns, I find it most appropriate to measure the abnormal return for pre-crisis and crisis periods. The use of abnormal return as a dependent variable aligns with the relevant literature surrounding this topic (Lins et al., 2017; Albuquerque et al., 2020; Ding et al., 2020; Takahashi & Yamada, 2020; Demers et al., 2021). Abnormal returns are calculated monthly as the difference between a firm's actual return and the expected return predicted by the CAPM. The formula is shown in equation (4).

$$MAR_{i,t} = r_{i,t} - E(r_{i,t}) \quad (4)$$

The abnormal return corrects for a stock's expected reaction to the market and reflects the unanticipated gain or loss generated by the specific stock. Abnormal returns are utilised instead of raw returns to discern the effects of ESG factors on stock performance, removing anticipated market fluctuations. While Demers et al. (2021) employ the Market Model (MM) for computing expected returns, I adopt the CAPM methodology, aligning with the approach of Albuquerque et al. (2020). Although the market model is viable for abnormal returns analysis, I favour CAPM due to its explicit incorporation of market risk and robust theoretical foundations. The return from the CAPM for firm *i*, at specific time *t*, is shown by equation (1) above.

4.6 Fixed Effects

To determine whether fixed or random effects were most appropriate for my regression model, I conducted a Hausman test. The test results indicated that the difference between the two specifications was negligible. Hence, I align with the existing literature, and proceed with fixed effects in my regression model. This decision ensures consistency with previous research and maintains the robustness of this analysis.

Fixed effects account for unobserved individual characteristics that do not change over time. This could include firm-specific factors for example. By including fixed effects, I control for these constant factors, ensuring that our analysis captures the specific effects of my independent variables, while accounting for individual differences across firms.

4.7 The Model

The literature presents a diverse array of methodologies. As mentioned in the literature review, among the key studies on this topic, Albuquerque et al. (2020) employ a cross-sectional model, focusing on the crisis period, defined as Q1 2020, while Lins et al. (2017) and Demers et al. (2021) opt for panel data analysis. Consistent with this strand of literature, my study investigates whether the impact of ESG scores varies across crisis and normal market conditions. This approach is inspired by Lins et al. (2017), who examined fluctuations in the effect of CSR across pre-crisis, crisis, and post-crisis periods during the 2008-2009 financial crisis. My model uses panel data with monthly observations for a sample of 469 firms from the S&P 500, for which ESG scores were available on Refinitiv. I split the sample into a pre-crisis dataset and a crisis period dataset. The pre-crisis period ranges from January 2017 to February 2020. The sample excludes firms that did not have ESG data available in addition to the exclusion of financial firms. Excluding financial firms from the sample helps maintain the homogeneity of the dataset, ensuring that the analysis focuses specifically on the impact of ESG on financial performance for non-financial firms. Financial firms tend to operate under different regulatory frameworks and derive revenue from distinct activities, potentially introducing bias into the analysis.

I use Panel data as it provides a significant advantage by accommodating both firm-specific and time-specific effects. By effectively controlling for these largely unobserved factors, panel data analysis reduces the risk of omitted variable bias and enhances the accuracy of inference (Stock & Watson, 2011). I use monthly observations to reduce noise arising from daily observations, while maintaining many observations to enhance the reliability of the study.

In contrast to Demers et al. (2021) and Takahashi and Yamada (2020), who employ Buy-and-Hold Abnormal Returns (BHAR) as their dependent variable, this analysis, due to the nature of panel data, necessitates a different approach. Following the methodology of studies by Lins et al. (2017) and Albuquerque et al. (2020), I use monthly abnormal returns as my dependent variable. A stock's expected return is calculated using the CAPM as stated above, and the regression model is listed below. The composition of each variable is given in Table A.1.

$$MAR = \beta_0 + \beta_1 DIESG + \beta_2 HML + \beta_3 SMB + \beta_4 Market_RF + \beta_5 Momentum + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

4.8 Robustness Checks

I conduct several robustness tests to check the coherence and sensitivity of the main findings. In addition, the main model will be tested using raw returns in both periods, depicted in Table A.2 and Table A.3.

Disaggregated ESG

As discussed in the literature review, Hoepner et al. (2016) emphasise that involvement in the environmental pillar of ESG is most successful in mitigating downside risk. In contrast, Albuquerque et al. (2020) only investigate the Environmental and Social dimensions of ESG to control for the governance effect, as well-managed companies typically allocate more resources to ES initiatives. To explore the impact of each dimension and counteract any potential governance effect, I employ disaggregated ESG scores in my analysis.

ESG Quartiles

By using quartiles, instead of a logged ESG scores, I examine whether the effect of a company's ESG score changes between different quartiles of ESG score. I regress abnormal returns on ESG score quartiles with dummies for quartiles 2 to 4 together with the Fama-French and momentum factors from the full model.

Heteroskedasticity

To assess the presence of heteroskedasticity in the panel regression model, I conducted a Breusch-Pagan test. The results indicated that none of the independent variables were statistically significant, suggesting that there is no evidence of heteroskedasticity in the panel data. This implies that the assumption of homoskedasticity is met, indicating that the variance of the error term is constant across all observations. Therefore, the regression model is robust against heteroskedasticity-related issues.

5.0 Data & Results

5.1 Data

The ESG data is based on the firm specific Refinitiv ESG score, obtained from Refinitiv DataStream. Fama-French factors are obtained from the Kenneth R. French Data Library. My return metrics are calculated using the DataStream Total Return Index (RI) obtained from Refinitiv DataStream. This index includes both capital appreciation and the reinvestment of dividends, providing a more accurate representation of investment performance, especially over the long term. All data is monthly.

The sample includes S&P 500 firms, restricted to include only equities active as of December 2021. The sample is further restricted by removing all firms for which there is insufficient availability of ESG data dating back to January 2017. In line with Fama & French (1993), financial institutions are omitted from my analysis as they typically operate with high levels of leverage. However, the implications of high leverage differ between financial and non-financial firms. In the former, high leverage is a common practice, while in the latter, it often signifies financial distress (Fama & French, 1993).

My dataset is based on monthly observations for the restricted sample of S&P 500 firms, which amounts to a cross-section of 469 firms. I only include firms for which there are observations for the entire period to ensure a balanced panel.

5.2 Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics for the 468 firms in the sample are given in Table 1 for the pre-crisis period and Table 2 for the crisis period. The main purpose of this dissertation is to ascertain the impact of ESG on the US stock market both prior to and during the COVID-19 shock. As such, my emphasis lies primarily on the dependent variable and the ESG variable rather than providing an extensive discussion on the other control variables. Notably, the ESG variable is the logged, differenced ESG score. As such when I interpret the ESG statistics I will transform them back into the raw score, to derive greater meaning. In the pre-crisis period, the average (median) logged ESG score is

4.089 (4.177), corresponding to an average raw ESG score of approximately 60 (65) out of a theoretical maximum of 100. Comparatively, in the crisis period, the average (median) logged score is 4.163 (4.224), corresponding to an average ESG score of 64 (68). Hence, on average firms scored higher in the crisis period. There is a significant difference in abnormal returns between the two periods, with firms outperforming expectations, on average exceeding expected return by 4%. In contrast, during the crisis, on average firms underperformed expectations by 0.28%.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics – Pre-Crisis Period

	Abnormal Returns	DIESG	Log_ESG	HML	SMB	Market_RF	Momentum
Observations	17822	17822	17822	17822	17822	17822	17822
Mean	4.004	0.004	4.089	-1.349	0.441	-0.415	0.649
Median	4.149	0.000	4.177	-1.670	0.960	1.190	0.040
75 th Percentile	4.296	0.000	4.363	0.300	1.130	3.120	3.260
25 th Percentile	3.895	0.000	3.910	-2.750	2.200	0.060	-1.540
Maximum	27.225	1.065	4.586	6.750	5.250	8.400	7.970
Minimum	-19.325	-0.452	2.389	13.870	4.830	-13.390	-8.680
Std. Deviation	1.156	0.053	0.365	3.218	2.353	4.423	3.564

A crucial takeaway from these statistics is that the standard deviation and interquartile range of abnormal returns is vastly different between the two periods, highlighting the volatility in the market over the crisis period. In the pre-crisis period, the interquartile range was approximately 0.4% indicating relatively low variability in the abnormal returns within this central portion of the dataset. This implies that a significant portion of the observations fall within a narrow range, suggesting some level of consistency or

stability in the abnormal return values. Conversely, in the crisis period, this interquartile range becomes vast at 9.43% reflecting higher variability and greater market uncertainty or volatility during the crisis. This significant increase in variability implies that abnormal returns experienced larger fluctuations and were less stable during the crisis period compared to the pre-crisis period.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics – Crisis Period

	Abnormal Returns	DIESG	Log_ESG	HML	SMB	Market_RF	Momentum
Observations	10318	10318	10318	10318	10318	10318	10318
Mean	-0.280	0.001	4.163	1.299	0.506	3.251	-0.677
Median	-0.573	0.000	4.224	0.050	0.490	2.910	0.550
75 th Percentile	4.264	0.000	4.333	3.260	2.470	5.580	2.450
25 th Percentile	-5.169	0.000	4.056	-2.200	2.330	-0.300	-2.600
Maximum	184.862	0.630	4.535	12.750	7.390	13.650	7.610
Minimum	-46.172	-0.265	3.082	-7.870	7.870	-4.370	-12.430
Std. Deviation	8.57	0.022	0.247	4.640	4.000	4.484	4.440

5.3 Correlation Matrices

Panels A and B of Table 3 illustrate the correlation between the regression variables for both pre-crisis and crisis periods. Panel A shows that in the pre-crisis period, the logged, differenced ESG score is the most positively correlated with abnormal returns.

All other variables except for momentum are negatively correlated, suggesting that higher values of HML, SMB, and the market risk premium are associated with lower abnormal returns. This implies that factors like firm size, book-to-market ratio, and

market risk premiums exert downward pressure on abnormal returns, indicating a potential risk-return trade-off where higher risk factors lead to lower abnormal returns.

Table 3:

Panel A: Correlation Matrix – Pre-Crisis Period

	Abnormal Returns	DIESG	HML	SMB	Market_RF	Momentum
Abnormal Returns	1					
DIESG	0.102	1				
HML	-0.028	-0.028	1			
SMB	-0.019	0.000	0.233	1		
Market_RF	-0.060	0.067	0.406	0.350	1	
Momentum	0.025	-0.031	-0.638	-0.332	-0.453	1

Panel B: Correlation Matrix – Crisis Period

	Abnormal Returns	DIESG	HML	SMB	Market_RF	Momentum
Abnormal Returns	1					
DIESG	-0.014	1				
HML	0.152	0.064	1			
SMB	-0.055	0.037	-0.240	1		
Market_RF	-0.169	-0.035	0.209	0.165	1	
Momentum	-0.011	0.020	-0.174	-0.223	-0.384	1

In contrast, in the crisis period, the correlation between abnormal returns and ESG reverses and becomes negative. All other variables except HML are also negative in the crisis period. Notably, in both periods, the correlation between all variables and abnormal returns is very weak suggesting that changes in any of the explanatory variables are not strongly associated with proportional changes in abnormal returns.

5.4 Pre-Crisis Results

Table 4: Pre-Crisis period abnormal returns regression. This table illustrates the results of regressing monthly abnormal returns on the firm specific Refinitiv ESG scores for the S&P 500 constituents in the sample from January 2017 to February 2020.

Table 4:	<i>Dependent Variable:</i>			
	Monthly Abnormal Returns (MAR)			
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
DIESG	0.556	-0.214	0.545	0.409
HML			0.084*** (0.017)	0.056*** (0.020)
SMB			0.069*** (0.023)	0.059** (0.023)
Market_RF			-0.169*** (0.013)	-0.057*** (0.013)
Momentum				-0.047** (0.019)
Constant	0.143*** (0.050)	0.146*** (0.050)	0.307* (0.056)	0.299*** (0.056)
Industry Fixed Effects	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	17822	17822	17822	17822
Adjusted R^2	0.00001	0.020	0.022	0.022
<i>Note:</i>		*p<0.1	**p<0.05	***p<0.01

In column (1) I regress MAR on the logged, differenced Refinitiv ESG score. In column (2) I add industry fixed effects. In column (3) I add the Fama-French factors. In column

(4) I add the momentum factor from the Carhart 4-factor model. Column (4) represents the full model. Robust standard errors are shown in parentheses.

Table 4 indicates that logged, differenced ESG scores are not significant at explaining the variation in abnormal returns in the pre-crisis period, even when running the complete model. These findings are consistent with much of the literature (Revelli and Viviani, 2015; Sargis and Wang, 2020) which find no significant relationship between ESG and abnormal returns in non-crisis periods.

Column (4) reveals all control variables are significant at the 5% level, with the value factor (HML) and market risk premium (Market_RF) significant at the 1% level. Notably, the coefficient for market risk premium is negative, suggesting that higher market risk premiums are associated with lower abnormal returns. This observation deviates from the existing literature on the topic. This may be attributed to the extensive timeframe of analysis, spanning back to 2017, a period marked by quantitative tightening in the US. This era likely witnessed heightened uncertainty, depressed stock valuations, and elevated market risk premiums, as investors sought higher returns to offset greater risk perceptions. The pronounced effect of the market risk premium aligns with asset pricing theory, reflecting investors' sensitivity to market-wide fluctuations and their expectations regarding future market movements. Similarly, the impact of the value factor on abnormal returns aligns with the efficient market hypothesis and the broader body of empirical evidence in finance literature.

5.5 Crisis Period Results

Table 5: Crisis period abnormal returns regression. This table illustrates the results of regressing monthly abnormal returns on the firm specific Refinitiv ESG scores for the S&P 500 constituents in my sample from March 2020 to December 2021. In column (1) I regress MAR on the logged, differenced Refinitiv ESG score. In column (2) I add industry fixed effects. In column (3) I add the Fama-French factors. In column (4) I add the momentum factor from the Carhart 4-factor model. Column (4) represents the full model. Robust standard errors are shown in parentheses.

Table 5:	<i>Dependent Variable:</i>			
	Monthly Abnormal Returns (MAR)			
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
DIESG	-9.110** (4.01)	-9.428** (4.08)	-12.504*** (4.05)	-9.438** (4.06)
HML			0.277*** (0.018)	0.214*** (0.020)
SMB			-0.013	-0.060** (0.029)
Market_RF			-0.169*** (0.016)	-0.225*** (0.018)
Momentum				-0.174*** (0.024)
Constant	-0.307*** (0.085)	-0.307*** (0.085)	0.166* (0.092)	0.269*** (0.093)
Industry Fixed Effects	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	10318	10318	10318	10318
Adjusted R ²	0.0004	0.009	0.039	0.044
<i>Note:</i>		*p<0.1	**p<0.05	***p<0.01

In the initial model (Column 1), focusing solely on changes in ESG scores, the coefficient for ESG is estimated at -9.110 with significance at the 5% level. This implies that a 1% increase in the logged, differenced ESG scores corresponds to a 9.1% decline in abnormal returns. Upon introducing industry fixed effects in Column 2, the coefficient for ESG remains significant (-9.428) but displays a slightly more negative effect due to this additional control. Expanding the model to include the Fama-French factors in Column 3, the coefficient for ESG becomes even more negative and achieves significance at the 1% level. Subsequently, with the inclusion of momentum in Column 4, all factors are significant at the 5% level, with all controls except SMB significant at the 1% level.

Similarly to the pre-crisis regression, the negative coefficient for the market risk premium (Market_RF) suggests a negative association with abnormal returns. This could be attributed to higher market risk premiums indicating greater market uncertainty

or volatility. During periods of heightened market risk, investors require higher returns to compensate for increased risk, resulting in downward pressure on stock prices. Given the realised return does not increase in line with the expected return, the abnormal return falls. This negative relationship reflects the risk-return trade-off principle, consistent with existing literature (Amah, 2024; Kinnunen, 2013). Furthermore, the negative association between abnormal returns and momentum suggests that stocks with recent positive performance tend to experience lower abnormal returns. This can be explained by mean reversion in stock prices, where the short-term trend of outperforming stocks may reverse as investors react to recent performance, resulting in lower abnormal returns as prices revert to sustainable levels. Additionally, the interpretation of the constant term varies across model specifications. In cases where only ESG is considered, it remains negative, indicating a baseline level of negative abnormal returns. However, upon incorporating the Fama-French factors and momentum, this baseline level becomes positive and significant at the 1% level. The adjusted R-squared values suggest improved explanatory power as more variables are added to the model, indicating enhanced understanding of variance in the dependent variable.

Overall, these results imply a significant negative relationship between changes in ESG scores and abnormal returns, even after controlling for other market factors and industry effects. These results are consistent with Demers et al., (2021) over this period, despite variations in our definitions of the crisis period. However, this negative relationship contradicts the findings of Lins et al. (2017). In their research, they found a significant positive impact of CSR on abnormal returns during the financial crisis, relative to pre- and post-crisis periods. This difference in our findings, could stem from the distinct origins of the crises. The financial crisis stemmed internally from banking and financial institutions, leading Lins et al. (2017) to propose that the social capital built up through CSR initiatives becomes particularly valuable when economic trust diminishes abruptly. However, a similar trust-related issue may not be relevant in the context of the COVID-19 crisis, which was triggered by an external shock. Consequently, it is plausible to infer that ESG might have a diminished impact during the COVID-19 crisis compared to the financial crisis. The negative relationship could instead stem from an agency theory perspective, initially proposed by Friedman (1970) and elaborated upon by Demers et al. (2021). This perspective suggests that executives might opt to enhance their company's ESG scores aiming to bolster their personal reputations to the detriment of shareholders.

It is also likely that, during crises, ethical investing takes a backseat, as investors prioritise maximising returns. Consequently, stocks with high ESG ratings may encounter inferior abnormal returns compared to their counterparts (Drange & Olav, 2021).

5.6 Disaggregated ESG

Table 6: This table illustrates the results of regressing monthly abnormal returns (MAR) on the firm specific Refinitiv ESG pillars for the S&P 500 constituents in my sample. Columns 1-3 represent the Pre-Crisis period, from January 2017 to February 2020. Columns 4-6 represent the Crisis Period, from March 2020 to December 2021. In column (1) I regress MAR on the logged, differenced environmental pillar score, using the full model. In column (2) I run the same model but for the social pillar in isolation. In column (3) I run the same model but for governance pillar score in isolation. I repeat this for the crisis period in columns 4-6. Robust standard errors are shown in parentheses.

The results from Table 6 show that even when disaggregating the pillars of ESG, no pillar is significant in explaining changes in abnormal returns for the pre-crisis period. The results are similar for the crisis period, with the results indicating that the coefficients for the environmental and social pillars are not significant, suggesting that the changes in environmental and social scores do not have a significant impact on monthly abnormal returns. However, the results reveal a negative coefficient for the governance pillar of -3.421, which is significant at the 10% level. This indicates that a 1% increase in governance scores are associated with approximately a -3.4% decrease in abnormal returns, albeit marginally significant. These findings somewhat oppose the findings Drange & Olav (2021), who find a similar negative relationship between ESG and abnormal returns but find that it is the environmental pillar of ESG that is most significant. All control variables remain significant at the 1% level for the pre-crisis period except SMB and Momentum which are significant at the 5% level. For the crisis period, all control variables except for SMB are significant at the 1% level. Additionally, the constant terms in all models provide the baseline abnormal returns when all other independent variables are zero. These constants are positive and statistically significant,

suggesting a baseline level of abnormal returns even in the absence of changes in ESG scores.

	<i>Dependent Variable:</i>					
	Monthly Abnormal Returns (MAR)					
	Pre-Crisis			Crisis		
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
DIEnv	0.145			0.373		
DISoc		1.634			-3.790	
DIGov			-0.553			-3.421* (1.886)
HML	0.056*** (0.020)	0.058*** (0.020)	0.055*** (0.020)	0.211*** (0.020)	0.212*** (0.020)	0.211*** (0.020)
SMB	0.059** (0.023)	0.059*** (0.023)	0.058** (0.023)	- 0.070*** (0.029)	- 0.065*** (0.029)	- 0.067*** (0.029)
Market_RF	0.056*** (0.013)	-0.058*** (0.013)	0.056*** (0.013)	- 0.225*** (0.018)	- 0.225*** (0.018)	- 0.225*** (0.018)
Momentum	-0.047** (0.019)	-0.046** (0.019)	-0.047** (0.019)	0.179*** (0.024)	0.177*** (0.024)	0.178*** (0.024)
Constant	0.299*** (0.056)	0.298*** (0.056)	0.300*** (0.056)	0.260*** (0.093)	0.264*** (0.093)	0.263*** (0.093)
Industry Fixed Effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	17822	17822	17822	10318	10318	10318
Adjusted R ²	0.022	0.022	0.022	0.044	0.044	0.044
<i>Note:</i>	*p<0.1	***p<0.01	**p<0.05			

5.7 ESG Quartiles

Table 7: This table presents the results from regressing abnormal returns on the logged ESG score by quartiles. Column (1) shows the results from the pre-crisis period and column (2) shows the results from the crisis period.

Dependent Variable: Monthly Abnormal Returns (MAR)		
	(1)	(2)
ESG_Quartile_2	-0.134	-1.123
ESG_Quartile_3	-0.178	-1.983* (1.071)
ESG_Quartile_4	-0.145	-2.763** (1.201)
HML	-0.009	0.216*** (0.020)
SMB	0.037	-0.074*** (0.029)
Market_RF	-0.074*** (0.014)	-0.225*** (0.018)
Momentum	-0.180*** (0.019)	-0.177*** (0.024)
Constant	0.426	2.033** (0.940)
Industry Fixed Effects	Yes	Yes
Observations	17822	10318
Adjusted R^2	0.021	0.044
<i>Note:</i>	* $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$	

As shown in Table 7, none of the ESG quartiles have a significant effect in the pre-crisis period. This supports the findings for the main model, indicating that the relationship between ESG scores and abnormal returns is consistent across different segments of the ESG distribution. This suggests that the observed relationship is robust and not driven by outliers or extreme values, providing evidence supporting the reliability of the main model's findings. Conversely, in the crisis period, I find that quartiles 3 and 4 are significantly negatively correlated with abnormal returns. This negative relationship is

again consistent with the findings for the main model in the crisis period. However, this highlights that the negative relationship in the main model is driven by firms that have higher ESG scores. This could indicate that firms prioritising ESG considerations may be sacrificing short-term financial performance for long-term sustainability, which may be reflected in stock prices below expectation, yielding lower abnormal returns.

6.0 Conclusion

This dissertation explores the impact of ESG on the stock market performance of US firms both prior to and during the COVID-19 crisis, assessing whether ESG functioned as a resilience factor. My findings reveal no significant relationship between ESG and stock market performance in regular market conditions. Conversely, the results suggest ESG has a significant negative effect on stock market performance and among the ESG factors, the governance dimension predominantly influenced this negative relationship. Furthermore, I find that this negative impact was particularly pronounced for firms scoring in the upper two quartiles of ESG ratings. This negative relationship contrasts with findings from other regions, suggesting that ESG's significance in the US may not be as pronounced as in other countries. Additionally, it provides evidence against claims from the investment industry that ESG acts as an “equity vaccine”. I believe this is due to the shift in investor sentiment during the crisis period. In periods of market uncertainty, as was the case in the COVID-19 crisis, investors may abandon ESG investments, shifting their priorities towards short-term gains and risk aversion. Hence, investors may prioritise liquidity and stability over long-term sustainability goals, leading them to divest from ESG assets in favour of less risky assets. Moreover, within the context of agency theory, if firms divert scarce resources into ESG investments to bolster their reputation at the expense of shareholder interests, this could prompt investors seeking capital preservation to divest from firms boasting high ESG scores.

These findings highlight the need to incentivise strong ESG performance during crises to meet global sustainability goals. Governments should consider providing incentives and rewards for companies that demonstrate strong ESG performance, by offering tax breaks, subsidies, or other financial incentives. Policymakers can encourage firms to prioritise sustainability initiatives without compromising financial performance, ultimately benefiting both investors and society.

6.1 Limitations and Scope for Future Research

The main limitation of this study is the lack of access to additional firm-level ESG score data, restricting the ability to cross-validate findings across different ESG scoring

providers. Relying solely on one provider, Refinitiv, may introduce bias or idiosyncrasies specific to their scoring criteria, potentially skewing the interpretation of results and limiting the generalisability of my findings. Nevertheless, Refinitiv assesses a broader array of metrics and indicators relative to its competitors, resulting in a thorough coverage of sustainability dimensions (Douglas et al., 2017). However, due to the large deviations in ESG scores across providers (Doyle, 2018; Berg et al., 2019), access to multiple providers would facilitate a more comprehensive analysis, enhancing the study's robustness and reliability. Additionally, the study's sample of S&P 500 constituents imposes a constraint by focusing only on large-cap firms, potentially overlooking the impact of ESG factors on smaller firms and sectors, thereby limiting the generalisability of findings to the broader US market.

Future research should conduct similar analyses for other regions, addressing the limitations of this study. Particularly, the existing literature on the impact of ESG on stock market performance in Europe remains limited, indicating scope for further exploration in future studies. Additionally, researchers could delve into comparative studies, exploring differences in the relationship between ESG and stock market performance across regions during crises. Such studies would shed light on the geographical variations in investors' perspectives on sustainable investing. Future research should also look to corroborate the conclusions drawn from this study, enhancing the credibility and robustness of the findings.

Appendix

Table A.1: Composition of Variables

MAR	Monthly abnormal returns, estimated using the CAPM. Betas obtained from Refinitiv DataStream
DIESG	Logged, differenced, Refinitiv ESG score
HML	Kenneth French's High Minus Low factor. It represents the spread in returns between companies with a high book-to-market value ratio (value companies) and companies with a low book-to-market value ratio.
SMB	Kenneth French's Small Minus Big factor. It measures the excess return of small-cap stocks over large-cap stocks.
Market_RF	Kenneth French's market factor. It represents the market risk premium.
Momentum	Kenneth French's momentum factor. Calculated as rolling, raw buy-and-hold returns of the past 12 months.

Table A.2: Pre-Crisis Period with Raw Returns

Pre-Crisis period raw returns regression. This table illustrates the results of regressing monthly abnormal returns on the firm specific Refinitiv ESG scores for the S&P 500 constituents in the sample from January 2017 to February 2020. In column (1) I regress raw returns on the logged, differenced Refinitiv ESG score. In column (2) I add industry fixed effects. In column (3) I add the Fama-French factors. In column (4) I add the momentum factor from the Carhart 4-factor model. Column (4) represents the full model. Robust standard errors are shown in parentheses.

	<i>Dependent Variable:</i>			
	Raw Returns			
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
DIESG	0.310	0.323	0.822	0.610
HML			0.082*** (0.020)	0.057*** (0.021)
SMB			0.057*** (0.023)	0.060** (0.022)
Market_RF			0.971*** (0.014)	0.956*** (0.014)
Momentum				-0.069** (0.020)
Constant	0.213*** (0.020)	0.213*** (0.020)	0.435*** (0.056)	0.421*** (0.056)
Industry Fixed Effects	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	17822	17822	17822	17822
Adjusted R^2	0.003	0.006	0.255	0.256
<i>Note:</i>		*p<0.1	**p<0.05	***p<0.01

Table A.3: Crisis Period with Raw Returns

Crisis period raw returns regression. This table illustrates the results of regressing raw returns on the firm specific Refinitiv ESG scores for the S&P 500 constituents in the sample from March 2020 to December 2021. In column (1) I regress raw returns on the logged, differenced Refinitiv ESG score. In column (2) I add industry fixed effects. In column (3) I add the Fama-French factors. In column (4) I add the momentum factor from the Carhart 4-factor model. Column (4) represents the full model. Robust standard errors are shown in parentheses.

	<i>Dependent Variable:</i>			
	Raw Returns			
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
DIESG	-16.537*** (5.008)	-16.989*** (5.170)	-12.192*** (4.051)	-9.058** (4.260)
HML			0.277*** (0.018)	0.212*** (0.020)
SMB			-0.024	-0.071** (0.030)
Market_RF			1.030*** (0.016)	0.973*** (0.018)
Momentum				-0.179*** (0.026)
Constant	2.729*** (0.106)	2.729*** (0.107)	0.207** (0.097)	0.312*** (0.098)
Industry Fixed Effects	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	10318	10318	10318	10318
Adjusted R^2	0.0004	0.009	0.324	0.327
<i>Note:</i>		*p<0.1	**p<0.05	***p<0.01

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